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Pp3c14_17190V3.1 CDS|P.patens -GVRRSLKVTSS-----RRR-SKGVRWGLGIAVGLVTGAI AAVILALL
Pp3c10_16000V3.1 CDS|P.patens -GVRRSLKAASK-----NRR-SKGARWGLGIAAGLVTGAVA AAVLLALI
CepurGG1.2G159700.1 CDS|C.purp -RLRRSLLSTSH-----KRR-SNGARWGLGIAVGLVTGAI AATLLALF
CepurGG1.3G182400.1 CDS|C.purp -APAPGPTQHAH-----RRHPSKATRWGVGFSLGTVAGAI IGILSGVV
Mapoly0115s0067.1 CDS|M.polymo -----QS-----SESNHRARKWALGLALGIVAGAI AALLATV
Smoell_97168 CDS|S.moellendorf -----IGAALGVIAGSVSGVLVGI I
Dicom.02G032700.1 CDS|D.compla -----PI-----RQKRHTSRRWALGLIVGFL LGVSGIICCVI
Dicom.02G032800.1 CDS|D.compla -----V-----RRKRHTARRWALGLILGLRAGILSGM TFVGT
Apun_EVM_utg0001171.20|Anthoc -AAAPGPLPR-----RKQSAQAQRWGLGLALGLVAGAVA AAMVATL
AagrOXF_EVM_utg0000281.95|Anth -AAAPGPLPR-----RKQSAQAQRWGLGLALGLVAGAVA AAMVATL
Azfi_s0148.g053104-mRNA-1-cds| -----YDHRSSLQTNTTDISTSKKQPQAIRWL VGVALGMVSGALTVLMFYGA
Sacu_v1.1_s0116.g021069-mRNA-1 -----FSSKNTGAGGTG--TTKKKHPRAVRWLVGIALGMAT GFVSAIVLSVA
Gb_16489|cds-8-10000835-100032 -----GKH-----KKKKHSTRRWALGLCIGIVAGAI SAVLSSFL
Gb_35408|cds-3-387812923-3878 -----GKH-----KKKKHPRRWALGLCIGIVAGAI FAVLSSFF
Gb_18261|cds-8-10098833-10101 -----GRH-----KKKKHSTRRWAWGLCMGIVSGAI SAVLSSFL
Thup1.29378695s0004.1 CDS|T.pl -----AEQHK-----KKKKQSAKKWALGMALGLVTGAI SAVLCSFL
Thup1.29380329s0004.1 CDS|T.pl -----TKH-----KKKKLPiKKWILGDALGLITGAI SAVMCTLL
Thup1.29377027s0006.1 CDS|T.pl -----TKH-----KKKKLPiKKWILGDALGVIAGAI SAFMCSFL
Thup1.29379777s0016.1 CDS|T.pl -----TKH-----KKKKLSITKWVLGGAIAI IIGQFSAIMCTFF
AmTr_v1.0_scaffold00166.7 CDS| -----HKK-----KKNRPLGGWILGFIVGTLAGFISAILFTLL
Aqcoe5G387700.1 CDS|A.coerulea ---LPALHHEH-----KKGENNAKGFVVGFFVGVASGMVSGFIC SLL
VIT_217s0000g09710.1 CDS|V.vin -----P---HKH-----RK-NKKLSAWILGFIAGAVAGCISGLV FSVL
Lsat_1_v5_gn_4_78640.1 CDS|L.s -----PSKKHKS-----K--TKKIIRWALGFLAGVIAGI ICGTIVSIL
HanXRQr2_Chr09g0411241|SOBIR1- -----PIHKHNK-----K--KKKVIRWILGFAAGTVAGL ICGSIVSVL
Lsat_1_v5_gn_1_28600.1 CDS|L.s -----QTPKHN-----KN-RKKTMGVILGFFVGVSVAGI ISAIILSVI
HanXRQr2_Chr04g0148411|CRN-2 -----PSKKHKK-----RN-RKKIMGWVLGFFAGS FAGILSIIIFSVL
HanXRQr2_Chr02g0050661|SOBIR1- -----PVRKHKK-----SS-RKKIMGWVLGFLAGSIAGI ISAMIISAL
orange1.1g006739m CDS|C.sinens -----HKHKK-----SK-GKKAAGWILGFIAGAVAGTISGFV FSVL
orange1.1g041655m CDS|C.sinens -----KA-----SS-GGKS-----KNVRQRFPTT
orange1.1g009595m CDS|C.sinens -----KE-----SS-GGKS-----TIVGQRF LTT
orange1.1g036970m CDS|C.sinens -----HK-NK-----HT-KRKL LGWILGFLAGALAGT LSGFVFSLL
orange1.1g046907m CDS|C.sinens -----VPAMHKRK-----NK-KRKLRSWFLGFLAGTFAGG ISAVLCSLL
Solyc06g071810.1.1 CDS|S.lycop -----PKQKHK-----NK-KKRIVEWILVFLAGTLAGSG SGLVFALL
MgTOL.D1881.1 CDS|M.guttatus_T -----PLLPKHKT-----NN-KRKLIAWILGFVAGAFAGILSGI IFSFL
MgTOL.O0343.1 CDS|M.guttatus_T APNAAPVHKNRK-----NK-AKKIASWILGFIAGAIAGSLSG FIFSL
Cucsa.196310.1 CDS|C.sativus v -----KLKKKKK-----SK-KKKVAAWILGFVVGAI GGTISGFVFSVL
AT2G31880.1 AtSOBIR1-1|A.thali -----VPVKDKH-----NKIRRKVGAWILGFFAGV FAGLSALIFSVL
Solyc03g111800.2.1 CDS|S.lycop -----PAHAHARAHH-----HK-KHRARNWVIGFFVGLFSGVLSG VLFSL
Acora.01G062800.1 CDS|A.americ -----HKH-----KNKKKRLIRWILEFSFGT LAVIICGTILYVL
HanXRQr2_Chr16g0727251|SOBIR1- -----AKEY-----GGVKALVSALMVSEA
orange1.1g037084m CDS|C.sinens -----HQN-----SEHKHNHREWILGFAIGWLLGMVFGVIF SVI
Nicol.B00799.1 CDS|N.colorata -----TSSH-----NR-TRKIWTWIVGFLVGIIVGVISGFITSA F
Zosma04g02530.1 CDS|Z.marina v -KNSSSGHHRH-----HSRKRLVRNWIVGFITGSITGILSG-----
GSMUA_Achr2T06010_001 CDS|M.ac -----GKHRS-----H--KHRVRNWIIGFVVGSLAGVVSGLAM SVL
LOC_Os06g18000.1 CDS|O.sativa ---DG--GRRHS-----H--KHRVRNWIIGFVVGSLAGVVISGLV LSVL
Sobic.010G120800.1 CDS|S.bicol ---T--GRHRS-----H--KNRVRNWIIGFVVGSLAGVISGMV LSVL
Zm00001d045785_T001 CDS|Z.mays ---GGQGKRHS-----HN-KHRVRNWIIGFVVGSLAGVISGLGMS VL
Bradi1g43417.1 CDS|B.distachyo -----TNRSSSEHHHS-----HSHKQSAARNWIVGFITGSLAGIVSGAVLS VL
MgTOL.A0684.1 CDS|M.guttatus_T -PNSSSEHHHS-----RSHKQSVRNWIVGFITGSLWGIISGIIL SVL
GSMUA_Achr6T28170_001 CDS|M.ac -----MSATFSEFFIGFTIGILLFFLWWSVVRLS
GSMUA_Achr6T28180_001 CDS|M.ac -----VGASVSEFAVGFALGIVAFVLRLLSVSCC
GSMUA_Achr8T28620_001 CDS|M.ac -----VGASVSEFAVCFALGTVAFVLRLLSVSCC
Aco027508.1 CDS|A.comosus v3|S -----
Aco009339.1 CDS|A.comosus v3|S -----

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